

The effect of one-dimensional core structure on thulium fiber laser properties

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ABSTRACT

Optical fibers for high-power thulium fiber lasers must meet several distinct requirements. A potential solution may lie in the concept of advanced fiber core structures. In this study, we fabricated and analyzed two double-clad thulium-doped optical fibers using modified chemical vapor deposition in combination with nanoparticle-doping methods to compare their spectroscopic and laser properties. The first fiber featured a uniformly doped core, while the second incorporated a radially segmented doping profile. The technological feasibility and suitability of this concept was experimentally tested.

Keywords: optical fiber, fiber laser, thulium, segmented-core, double-clad, nanoparticle doping

1. INTRODUCTION

High power thulium-doped fiber lasers^{1,2} (TDFL) operating at wavelengths around 2 micrometers have a wide range of potential applications, from medicine³ to defense⁴ and material processing⁵. Double-clad thulium-doped fibers (TDF), preferred for such fiber lasers, must meet a variety of often conflicting spectroscopic or technological requirements. In addition to low background losses⁶ or satisfactory fluorescence lifetime⁷, a sufficiently high concentration of thulium ions (Tm^{3+}) and suitable co-dopants⁸ in the fiber core is necessary for achieving high-power laser operation with high efficiency. The two-for-one cross-relaxation process in TDF has the potential to significantly increase laser efficiency⁹. However, increasing the Tm^{3+} doping concentration above 3.5 wt.%¹⁰ presents several technological challenges and performance trade-offs.

Pair induced quenching process can be mitigated by incorporating co-dopants such as Al_2O_3 or P_2O_5 , which help prevent thulium clusters formation. Despite this, energy transfer up-conversion^{9,11} is inevitable and can be reduced by lowering the local population of metastable levels. These effects, combined with increased heat generation due to high pump absorption (exceeding 300 watts per meter in the fiber core¹²), significantly reduce laser efficiency. To mitigate the heat load, advanced fiber fabrication techniques, including structured or segmented-core fiber designs¹³ have been explored. These designs aim to reduce the spatial overlap between the propagating core mode and the thulium-doped region. These fibers ensure high local thulium ion concentration for the desired two-for-one process, while maintaining an average concentration low enough to reduce the unwanted heat load.

In this study, we compare two types of double-clad silica-based TDFs with quasi-octagonal profile of inner cladding. We tested both a conventional uniformly doped fiber and a segmented-core fiber, in which Tm^{3+} ions are confined to a central region around the core axis.

2. EXPERIMENT

The fibers used in this study were drawn from optical preforms fabricated using a modified chemical vapor deposition technique in combination with nanoparticle doping. A uniformly doped fiber (denoted #1) was prepared as a step-index fiber, utilizing a single porous SiO_2 layer doped with Tm^{3+} and Al_2O_3 . A segmented-core fiber (denoted #2) was prepared by deposition of GeO_2 -doped layer prior to the deposition of the active center (doped with Tm^{3+} and Al_2O_3). The refractive index of the germanate layer was matched to the doped section. Both fibers were drawn as single-mode fibers and coated

with a fluorinated acrylate coating with dimensions comparable to commercially available fiber optic components (10/130 μm core/cladding diameter). The inner cladding of prepared fibers had a quasi-octagonal geometry to break the circular symmetry and enable efficient transfer of pump radiation from the cladding to the fiber core.

Drawn fibers were characterized using a commercially available refractive index profiler (IFA-100, Interfiber Analysis Inc.) equipped with a laser source emitting at 975 nm. A one-dimensional (1D) profile was created by passing the laser beam through a fixed fiber position, and the final profile was averaged over multiple scans to minimize experimental errors. A two-dimensional (2D) profile was reconstructed from 36 single scans while rotating the fiber around its axis. The fibers were further characterized in terms of attenuation and spectral absorption. A tungsten halogen lamp was used as a broadband radiation source. Small-signal (core) absorption was measured using several-centimeter-long sections of active fibers spliced with standard single-mode fibers. For cladding absorption, several-meter-long sections were spliced with multimode fibers to excite the larger cladding regions. Fluorescence lifetimes were measured using a Lumics LU793MU250 diode emitting at 792 nm as an excitation source, along with a Hamamatsu InGaAs photodiode detector and Thorlabs PDA36A Si detectors. Millimeter-long fiber samples were used for this measurement. The decay curves were measured using a side detection setup¹⁴. Finally, the fibers were tested in a Fabry-Perot laser configuration. Tested TDFs were pumped at 792 nm using a 50 W laser diode (BWT, 105/125 μm). The output power was measured using a Thorlabs S425C-L power meter. A Thorlabs fiber (FG105UCA, 105/125 μm , NA 0.22), characterized by high transmission at 792 nm and high attenuation within the 1900-2000 nm spectral range, was used to protect against back-reflected emissions. A high-reflectivity fiber Bragg grating (HR FBG), reflecting at 1940 nm (TeraXion, 10/130 μm), was spliced with passive fiber (SM-GDF, 10/130 μm , NA 0.15) to improve the mode field diameter mismatch. The output coupler was formed by Fresnel reflection from a perpendicularly cleaved fiber end. A silicon filter was used to separate the laser emission from the unabsorbed pump power and the laser spectra were recorded using a Thorlabs OSA203C optical spectrum analyzer.

3. RESULTS

The initial objective was to verify the technological feasibility of the proposed fiber designs. Subsequently, the manufactured fibers were evaluated to compare the effects of different core structures on their spectroscopic properties and laser performance. Fiber#1 was drawn with a 5.9/120 μm core/cladding diameter, while Fiber#2 featured a doped core region with a diameter of 3.3 μm (5.7/120 core/cladding diameter), see Fig.1b. The ratio of doped to undoped core area was thus approximately 1/3. All measured parameters are summarized in Table 1:

Table 1. Relevant parameters of fibers under study.

	Matrix	$\tau_{(3F4)}$ [μs]	$\tau_{(3H4)}$ [μs]	Losses [dB/km]	Core abs. [dB/m]	Clad abs. [dB/m]	avg. Tm^{3+} [mol. ppm]	MFD [μm]	NA	$\lambda_{\text{cut-off}}$ [μm]
Fiber#1	Tm: Si-Al	563	27.7	21	265	1.1	~ 8000	6.7	0.24	1.57
Fiber#2	Tm: Si-Al-Ge	517	29.5	19	69	0.13	~ 2000	6.1	0.27	1.68

Significant differences in core and cladding absorption between tested fibers were observed. The average Tm^{3+} concentrations in the fiber core were estimated from the measured absorption peaks at 1640 nm, taking into account the overlap factors between guided mode and doped areas (0.782 for Fiber#1 and 0.812 Fiber#2).

The cladding absorption measured at wavelength of 792 nm revealed even more pronounced differences, highlighting variations in pump absorption efficiency between the two fibers.

The fluorescence lifetime values were consistent with those observed for highly-doped nanoparticle-doped fibers with high contents of both thulium and alumina⁷. Fiber#1 exhibited slightly higher lifetime values (corresponding to the 3F4 level), indicating less concentration quenching and multiphonon relaxation. Overall, Fiber#1 demonstrated better spectroscopic quality, indicating less detrimental interaction between thulium ions.

Fig. 1a shows the refractive index profile (RIP) of the uniformly doped fiber, with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 5.9 μm and a refractive index change of 19.8×10^{-3} along the fiber axis. The insets provide full 2D views of the fiber's internal RIP: left inset demonstrates the quasi-octagonal shape of the inner cladding, while the right inset presents a detailed view of the doped region. Fig. 1b clearly shows the core structure of Fiber#2, where the doped central region ($\Delta n \sim 4.6 \times 10^{-3}$) is surrounded by undoped germanate layer ($\Delta n \sim 20 \times 10^{-3}$) which matches well with the doped region of Fiber#1.

Fig. 1. RIP of a) uniformly doped fiber. Inset: cross-sectional views of the full (left) and detailed (10x10 μm , right) regions, b) segmented-core fiber

Figs. 2a and 2b show the laser output power at 1940 nm as a function of absorbed pump power. For Fiber#1, the maximum laser output power reached 9.6 W, with a slope efficiency (SE) of 48 % with respect to absorbed power and a laser threshold of 0.9 W. It is important to note that the pump laser diode was limited to 30 W, resulting in an absorbed pump power of ~ 21 W. For Fiber#2, a maximum output power of 8 W was achieved at the same pump power, with a laser threshold of 0.7 W and a slightly lower SE of 41.7 % with respect to absorbed pump power. The optimized fiber length for Fiber#2 was 20 m, which is more than 3 times longer compared to Fiber#1. This observation confirms earlier findings of very weak absorption in the cladding and low average concentration of Tm^{3+} ions in fiber core, which limits the efficiency of the two-for-one process. Despite the use of a very long resonator, no parasitic lasing was observed, and laser emission remained stable, as shown in the inset of Fig. 2b.

Fig. 2. Lasing characteristics of a) uniformly doped fiber for optimal fiber length of 6 m, with a laser threshold of 0.9 W, b) segmented-core fiber for fiber length of 20 m, with a laser threshold of 0.7 W.

When comparing the spectroscopic and laser properties, it seems that the spatially smaller and lower-doped core of the segmented structure negatively affects the pumping absorption. This results in a non-optimally long length of laser resonator. However, this experiment serves as a technological proof of principle. With an optimized ratio of doped to undoped core regions, this fiber structure has the potential to be suitable for fiber lasers operating at longer wavelengths within the thulium emission band. The data supporting the results of this study are available in¹⁵.

4. CONCLUSION

We reported the design and fabrication of two double-clad TDF featuring uniformly doped and segmented-doped fiber cores. A comparative study was conducted to evaluate their spectroscopic properties, refractive index profiles, and laser performance. The segmented-core structure revealed key effects on the optical and laser properties of the fiber. The uniformly doped fiber achieved a laser efficiency of 48%, while the segmented-core fiber exhibited a slightly lower efficiency (approximately 6% lower), but with a lower laser threshold. These findings suggest that the segmented-core design, with further optimization, could enhance fiber laser performance at longer wavelengths within the thulium emission band. This study offers a promising avenue for future developments in high-power thulium-doped fiber laser technology.

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REFERENCES

1. M. N. Zervas and C. A. Codemard, "High Power Fiber Lasers: A Review," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics* **20**, 219–241 (2014) [doi:10.1109/jstqe.2014.2321279].
2. F. Todorov et al., "Active optical fibers and components for fiber lasers emitting in the 2- μ m spectral range," *Materials* **13**(22), 5177 (2020) [doi:10.3390/ma13225177].
3. M. Michalska et al., "Highly stable, efficient Tm-doped fiber laser—a potential scalpel for low invasive surgery," *Laser Phys. Lett.* **13**(11), 115101 (2016) [doi:10.1088/1612-2011/13/11/115101].
4. S. D. Jackson, "Towards high-power mid-infrared emission from a fibre laser," *Nature Photon* **6**(7), 423–431 (2012) [doi:10.1038/nphoton.2012.149].
5. I. Mingareev et al., "Principles and applications of trans-wafer processing using a 2- μ m thulium fiber laser," *Int J Adv Manuf Technol* **84**(9–12), 2567–2578 (2016) [doi:10.1007/s00170-015-7870-z].
6. M. P. Buckthorpe and W. A. Clarkson, "Simple method for determining quantum efficiency and background propagation loss in thulium-doped fibres," *Appl. Phys. B* **129**(9), 142 (2023) [doi:10.1007/s00340-023-08084-x].
7. P. Vařák et al., "Luminescence and laser properties of RE-doped silica optical fibers: The role of composition, fabrication processing, and inter-ionic energy transfers," *Optical Materials: X* **15**, 100177 (2022) [doi:10.1016/j.omx.2022.100177].
8. W. Blanc et al., "Thulium environment in a silica doped optical fibre," *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **354**(2–9), 435–439 (2008) [doi:10.1016/j.jnoncrysol.2007.06.083].
9. S. D. Jackson, "Cross relaxation and energy transfer upconversion processes relevant to the functioning of 2 μ m Tm³⁺-doped silica fibre lasers," *Optics Communications* **230**(1–3), 197–203 (2004) [doi:10.1016/j.optcom.2003.11.045].
10. Y. Wang et al., "High power tandem-pumped thulium-doped fiber laser," *Opt. Express* **23**(3), 2991 (2015) [doi:10.1364/OE.23.002991].
11. D. A. Simpson et al., "Energy transfer up-conversion in Tm³⁺-doped silica fiber," *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **352**(2), 136–141 (2006) [doi:10.1016/j.jnoncrysol.2005.11.019].
12. M. Grábner, P. Peterka, and P. Honzátko, "Formula for temperature distribution in multi-layer optical fibres for high-power fibre lasers," *Polish Academy of Sciences and Association of Polish Electrical Engineers in cooperation with Military University of Technology* (2021) [doi:10.24425/OPELRE.2021.139482].
13. M. J. Barber et al., "Nested-ring doping for highly efficient 1907 nm short-wavelength cladding-pumped thulium fiber lasers," *Opt. Lett.* **45**(19), 5542 (2020) [doi:10.1364/OL.401228].
14. M. Kamradek et al., "Nanoparticle and solution doping for efficient holmium fiber lasers," *IEEE Photonics J.* **11**(5), 1–10 (2019) [doi:10.1109/JPHOT.2019.2940747].
15. J. Aubrecht, "Dataset for: The effect of one-dimensional core structure on thulium fiber laser properties," *Zenodo* (2025) [doi:10.5281/ZENODO.14921971].